

Alliance Data Officers' Group Meeting

Wednesday 18th June 2025, 11:00am to 12:30pm

This is a summary of the key points, outcomes and actions from the UK Health Data Research Alliance Data Officers' Group (DOG).

Summary of Actions

Actions	Lead
Laura Sato to give more details on National Reusable Code Catalogue (for reference) and Library (open git - actual code) at the next Data officers meeting.	Data standards Team
Explore the inclusion of QUANTUM metrics in the HDR UK Gateway with practical examples (within 6–9 months).	Data standards and Technology team
Date for the next Data Officers Group meeting to be confirmed and scheduled promptly	Data standards Team
Promote the CARROT mapper Community monthly meeting to increase visibility.	Alliance and Data standards team

Welcome and Introductions

The meeting started with an introduction from the Chair, who welcomed data officers, encouraging them to introduce themselves in the chat, and outlined the agenda for the meeting.

Alliance Updates

The Chair noted that Alliance membership continues to expand, with the alliance welcoming 13 new [members](#) since the last DOG and now comprising 121 members.

He encouraged Alliance members to mention any issues they want to feed into the Alliance council meeting (8th July).

Looking ahead, the upcoming **OHDSI UK 2025** meeting was announced, scheduled **for 26th September** at the Wellcome Trust. Booking details are available via the HDR UK Alliance website.

DDA Update and Quantum Overview-Data Quality and Maturity Label (Monica Jones-HDR UK)

Presentation Slides

- An update was given on the HDR UK Data Design Authority, which is currently revising the **2021 white paper**, “Recommendations for Data Standards in Health Data Research” with a focus on progress made, especially around OMOP adoption. Structured interviews and consultations are in progress, aiming for publication by year-end. Two supporting working groups were noted, including one on curated data and another on federated metadata, now being reformed under new leadership.
- The presentation covered the QUANTUM project, which runs from 2024–2026 and supports Article 78 of the European Health Data Space Regulation by developing a data quality and maturity label to standardise data quality across the EU.
- The data quality label has been developed through literature reviews, Delphi processes, and stakeholder engagement, and comprises 12 core dimensions. It has been deployed via an online tool and is currently undergoing a mid-scale pilot across 35 European institutions.
- The data maturity model, which was based on HDR UK’s Data Utility Framework, assesses data holders’ readiness for the EU Health Data Space. It includes 10 dimensions and five maturity levels, aligned with international standards. Now part of EU legislation, it is being piloted, with upcoming work focused on training, use cases, and integration.
- Although the UK is not obligated to adopt the framework post-Brexit, potential benefits include improved interoperability, alignment with global standards, and stronger involvement in collaborative research. Discussions on future UK alignment are ongoing.

Discussion

Questions were raised regarding the application of the QUANTUM metrics to UK datasets. It was confirmed that while the UK was not included in the initial small-scale pilot, some UK organisations are participating in the current mid-scale pilot. Supporting materials, including online tools and user guides, are already available and being tested during this phase. Feedback to date has indicated the tools are user-friendly and effective.

Interest was expressed in integrating Quantum metrics into UK infrastructure, such as displaying them within the Health Data Research UK Gateway to enable dataset comparisons across Europe. This is being considered, with plans to develop worked examples in the coming months.

A further question concerned the challenge of assessing complex, content-rich datasets such as imaging data. It was acknowledged that while the framework is based on self-assessment, benchmarking across participating organisations and future collaboration on defining technical standards would support consistency. Ongoing work aims to address these challenges, and further engagement with the technical team was offered for more detailed discussion.

OMOP Mapping Quality -OMOP Tools for Mapping Data to OMOP (Tri Thien Nguyen - University of Nottingham)

[\[Presentation Slides\]](#)

- This presentation was given on tools developed at the University of Nottingham to support the mapping of healthcare data to the OMOP Common Data Model. The speaker outlined the challenges in OMOP data mapping, including manual effort, duplication across organisations, and inconsistent standards that hinder international collaboration.
- Existing tools were discussed, noting limitations such as lack of code generation or restricted deployment. In response, Nottingham developed Carrot, [a toolset designed to facilitate OMOP mapping and ETL processes](#). It comprises Carrot Mapper, a web-based application for generating mapping rules, and Carrot Transform, an ETL engine that applies these rules to convert source data to OMOP CDM.
- Key features include manual and automated concept mapping, reuse of existing mappings, and automatic rule generation based on OMOP domains. The tools are open-source, user-friendly, collaborative, and require no SQL scripting. They are already in use by several UK institutions including the University of Dundee and Public Health Scotland.
- While Carrot offers a comprehensive solution, some limitations remain, such as limited support for custom CDMs and a need for better provenance tracking. Future development plans include improved deployment using Kubernetes and potential AI integration for concept recommendation.

Discussion

It was noted that one site had used a commercial partner to develop bespoke SQL scripts for OMOP mapping, but in hindsight, the newer toolset presented by the Nottingham team offers a more sustainable and promising approach.

Interest was expressed in promoting the [Carrot Community monthly meeting](#), which had not been widely known. It was suggested that HDR UK and the Alliance could help advertise this to the wider community.

A question was raised about whether current mapping tools allow users to record the quality or confidence level of individual mappings. The Nottingham team confirmed this functionality is planned for the near future.

Data Curation and project support in British Heart Foundation-Data Science Centre (BHF-DSC) (John Nolan-BHF-DSC)

[Presentation Slides](#)

- This presentation focused on the CVD-COVID-UK COVID-IMPACT Consortium, a data resource enabling studies on the effects of COVID-19 on cardiovascular disease. Researchers can access a range of datasets including primary care, secondary care,

prescribing records, death records, disease registries, and COVID-19 testing and vaccination data.

- A key emphasis was placed on the data curation phase, which can account for up to 80% of a research project's duration. The team defines **data curation as the transformation of raw or provisioned data into analysis-ready datasets through processes such as data filtering, summarisation, phenotyping, cleaning, and harmonisation.**
- The presentation highlighted the use of curated research-ready data assets developed to promote quality and consistency, including:
 - A harmonised demographics table combining five datasets to improve completeness (e.g., ethnicity recording improved from 60% to over 90%)
 - A COVID-positive table integrating COVID-19 records from multiple sources, annotated with severity indicators
 - An LSOA table enabling geographic tagging for environmental and deprivation analysis
 - A measurements table standardising clinical measurements across time and units
- The team also supports projects by signposting researchers to existing curated resources and reusable code, providing detailed guidance on data workflows and pipeline development, conducting data explorations, particularly for complex or underused datasets (e.g., maternity and mental health), and in some cases, developing full or partial pipelines on behalf of project teams.
- The goal is to enable and upskill researchers to develop their own pipelines through the use of centralised code repositories, curated assets, and documentation. Increasingly, the team is moving towards a model of guidance and resource provision rather than hands-on pipeline creation.

Discussion

A discussion opened with strong appreciation of the team's work and its critical support to researchers using the national Secure Data Environment (SDE). It was clarified that although the team's tools and resources have primarily supported cardiovascular disease (CVD) and COVID-19 focused projects, the expertise and resources are not restricted to these areas. The team is open to supporting other research domains, with a costing model under development to enable external teams to purchase support.

The challenge of transferring code and pipelines developed within the NHS England SDE to other platforms or projects was addressed. Currently, moving code between environments is cumbersome and manual. However, efforts are underway to test a code-sharing facility within NHS England that would enable easier transfer of code across different agreements, a functionality considered important to avoid duplicated effort in future projects.

A question was raised regarding the inclusion of unstructured or free-text data within the data sets. It was explained that free-text data is not currently included due to data sharing agreement restrictions aimed at reducing risk of patient identification. Free-text fields are automatically excluded, and sensitive fields such as exact dates of birth are generalized. While free text is not

part of the current data provision, other parts of the broader Data Science Centre are working on projects involving such data.

Ensuring Data Integrity: Data Quality and Governance (Jessica Jenkins- Experian)

Presentation

- This presentation outlined Experian's evolving role in health data research, with a particular focus on data quality services. Historically recognised for credit reporting, Experian now supports NHS England, the Department of Health and Social Care, and NHS Trusts through data cleansing and validation solutions.
- The speaker introduced Aperture Data Studio, a tool developed to streamline data quality processes. It enables organisations to ingest data from multiple formats, standardise and cleanse it, and then monitor its integrity through configurable rule-based queries. The platform is low/no-code, supports interoperability via APIs, and can be deployed on-premises or securely off-site.
- Experian has been working with partners including AstraZeneca to support clean data environments for initiatives such as clinical trials and patient recruitment. The aim is to help organisations ensure data completeness, remove duplication, and maintain accuracy across complex systems.
- Although the specific alignment with current health data research projects remains exploratory, the presentation served as an introduction to Experian's capabilities and opened the door for future collaboration opportunities.

Discussion

There was emphasis on the potential for collaboration between clinical, academic, and commercial sectors to drive progress. It was suggested that commercial partners interested in working with HDR UK could benefit from being involved more broadly in alliance activities.

Attending Organisations

1. Barts Health NHS Trust
2. Cancer Research UK
3. Cystic Fibrosis Trust
4. Economic and Social Research Council
5. Ernst and Young UK
6. Experian
7. Foresight Research
8. Genomics England
9. Health and Social Care Northern Ireland
10. Health Data Research UK
11. Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust
12. Imperial College NHS Trust
13. Intensive Care National Audit and Research Centre
14. Leeds Teaching Hospital
15. NICE

The logo for the UK Health Data Research Alliance features a stylized square frame composed of four L-shaped corner brackets. The top-left and bottom-right corners are light blue, while the top-right and bottom-left corners are a darker blue. The text "UK Health Data Research Alliance" is centered within this frame in a bold, black, sans-serif font.

**UK Health Data
Research Alliance**

16. NHS England
17. Nottingham University
18. Our Future Health
19. Research Data Scotland
20. Royal College of General Practitioners
21. tech UK
22. The Brain Tumour Charity
23. The University of Edinburgh
24. University of Leeds
25. University of Aberdeen
26. University of Dundee
27. University of Oxford